

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

MODERN AMELIORATIVE STATE OF SOILS IN THE KURDAMIR REGION

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Abstract

Rapid growth of population, increase of the agricultural plants due to the need for food products and improvement of the ameliorative state of soils under cultivation are an important problem of the day. From this point of view, the information about the soils in the experimental area selected in the Kurdamir region of the Shirvan plain was given in the presented article. The soils have heavy granulometric composition and meadow-grey type. According to the analysis results, the salt quantity of the undergrain soils was 0.10-0.59 % and this indicates that the experimental soils were non-salinized, they were salinized weakly and moderately. Generally, the irrigation norms should be followed correctly in order to protect ameliorative state and fertility of the soils.

Keywords: irrigated, ecological, fertility, salinization, salinity degree.

INTRODUCTION

Presence of the favourable climate, soil, hydrogeological condition is important in order to use soil efficiently in agricultural production. Increase of the soil fertility, higher, stable agricultural production, regulation of the water, heat and food regimes is possible due to soil amelioration measures. The soil fertility mostly depends on water and air regimes. In order to provide plants with fertility factors without interruption, the soil should have the amount of moisture required by the plants [2]. The ameliorative state of soils are also formed under the influence of the natural factors and irrigation economic system. The soil cover, climate situation, geological and geomorphological structure, irrigation water, hydrological and hydrogeological standard of the zone belong to the natural factors forming ameliorative state in the soil. The main indications which characterize ameliorative state of soils are considered salinization and solonchification degrees, salinity type, sort, state of the soil solution, depth of the groundwater location, mineralization degree, irrigated water quality, earth relief, natural and artificial draining level [1]. Metternicht G.İ. and other researches show that the soil salinization creates serious ecological risk as a result of the natural or technogen processes at present [7].

The Kur-Araz lowland possessing a good condition for growing of the main agricultural plants and study of the ameliorative state of these soils in the country are an important problem. The Shirvan plain is situated in the Kur-Araz lowland and the researches were performed in the Kurdamir district [3].

RESEARCH OBJECT AND METHOD

The experimental area was selected as a research object in the undergrain soils and the soil samples were

taken from the characteristic places (the coordinates were noted) in the Sorsor village of the Kurdamir region. The chemical analyses in the taken soil samples were fulfilled according to the wide-spread method in the republic [3].

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

At present the soil reform in the republic aims to radically increase the efficiency of agro-industrial production and improve the population's food supply. Rationality of the irrigation and amelioration systems is of special importance because of the agricultural production in the irrigated soils. The international experiment indicates that the priorities for achieving efficiency in irrigated agriculture depend on economical development standard, physical state of the irrigation and amelioration systems, including exploitation organisation and other factors. The population growth and aggravation of the ecological environment, including the observed global climatic changes require improvement of population with the qualitative food products in conditions of decrease of the fruitful soil funds and drinkable water resources, increase and intensification of the agricultural production. The basis of the irrigation agriculture is grain-growing, fodder-growing and cotton-growing in the country.

The agricultural production is obtained due to irrigations and the Kur-Araz lowland is a basic irrigated zone of the country. The soil-cover of the lowland is formed under the influence of the local factors and sufficiently colorful. As is known there are different salts in the soil and they differ for their toxicity. The classification of salts for their saltiness rate and type was given by some scientists. V.R.Volobuyev divided lowland soils into types according to their salinization: sodium, chloride-sodium, chloride-calcium-magnesium,

sulphate-calcium, carbonate-calcium [9]. Recently, G.Z.Azizov divided the soils into salinity types: sodium, chloric, sulphate-chloric, chloric-sulfate and sulfate. After G.Z.Azizov, L.Z.Jalilova specified classification of the sulfatic salinized soils for saltiness rate and type in the Shirvan plain and showed chloric-sulfatic-natrium, sulfatic-natrium (gypsum 1-2%), sulfatic (gypsum >2.0%) [4,5].

At present the most worrying issue is global climate change by the world countries and some international organisations and global research centers. The global climate changes affect different countries, including Azerbaijan. Desertification and soil degradation increased because of increase of temperature, floods, decrease of the river waters[6].

The researches were performed in the Kurdamir region located in the Shirvan plain. The Kurdamir belongs to the lowland economic region. A zone of the region is 163151 hectare and its main activity is plant-growing and cattle-breeding. A relief of the Kurdamir region is a plain and most of the area is below sea level. The climate –summer is drought mild hot semi-desert and dry steppe type. Here, the river network is sparse. The low flows of the Girdiman and Agsu rivers are in Kurdamir. The slope of the region is 1 degree, The calculations indicate that the altitude above sea level is 0-200 m (on depth and height scale), a moderate yearly

temperature is 15⁰ C, a yearly quantity of rains is 250-300 mm, the wind velocity 2-3 m/sec, dry subtropical climate [8]. Vegetation of the zone is different. Mainly, grey-meadow, grey and meadowe-grey soils spread. The calculations indicate that the moderate, strong salinized and saline soil areas constitute approximately 7.2 % of the non-salinized and weak saline soils. The soils are heavy by granulometric composition and they are calcareous along the whole profile. An absorption capacity of the same soils is high. The soils of the research area belong to meadow-grey soil type and the salt quantity was defined to study ameliorative state of soils in them. According to the results, the salt number in the undergrain soils was 0.10-0.58%. CO₂ ion wasn't in anion composition of salts. HCO₂ ion was 0.012-0.058%, Cl ion was 0.014-0.171%. SO₄ion was 0.012-0.384%, Ca -0.020-0.057%, Mg-0.003-0.017% and Na+K was 0.002-0.125% in the salt cation composition. The consequences were shown in a graphic form. As we know, different types of salts exist in soil. Therefore, it was determined which type the salts belong to. The consequences indicate that the salts belong to sulphatic, chlorine-sulfatic type. The salt quantity in the experimental soils was shown in the following graphic. Productivity of the grain plant was 29-30 s/h in the experimental soils.

Graphic. Change graphic of salts in the experimental soils

Generally, the ecological changes happened in recent times affected ameliorative state of soils and the degradation processes in them accelerated as a result of these changes. For this purpose, it is important to conduct extensive researches for protection of the ameliorative state and fertility in soils. But the last investigations indicate that hydrogeological-ameliorative state of the irrigated soils improved noticeably and this is the result of the implementation of purposeful reclamation measures [10,11].

CONCLUSION

1. During the researches it was determined that the salt number of the undergrain soils was 0.10-0.59 % in

the experimental areas. The same soils are sulfatic and chlorine-sulfatic for the salt type.

2. It was determined that the soils in the experimental areas were non-salinized, weak and moderate salinized according to the obtained consequences. The productivity was 28-30 s/h in grain plant.

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